

THE EXPERIENCE OF SOUTH KOREA AND CHINA IN THE ORGANIZATION OF HIGHER EDUCATION ORGANIZATIONS

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The development of educational organizations in our country and the experience of developed foreign countries in this regard show that other countries have accumulated a lot of positive experience in the organization of higher education, especially private higher education.

It is appropriate to use the advanced experience of foreign countries in the organization and development of private higher education in our country.

In particular, 42% of the working-age population in China aged 25-65 has a higher education, which is characterized by the fact that production in the country is highly automated and requires a higher level of training than ordinary workers.

Today, the country has 615 universities, including 425 private universities, where 2.5 million students study. China's higher education system is unique, and despite all the changes that have taken place in recent decades, it remains the most conservative in the world.

At the same time, the renewal of Chinese society is taking place through the reform of the education system. The reform initiated by the government in 2001 envisages the unification of higher education institutions into university corporations with relatively greater independence.

Not only did the corporations take ownership of the university buildings and land, but they also gained virtually complete autonomy.

According to the authors of these reforms, not only higher educational institutions increase their responsibility for the quality of their diplomas, but also encourage the management to strengthen activities aimed at establishing relations between science and business. Corporations take full advantage of the opportunity to create their own programs and curricula, to determine the specialization of their university, and to pursue policies of free liberalization and diversification.

A multi-level higher education system has been formed in China, and the number of higher education institutions in the country has been increasing dramatically in recent years. To date, the number of public universities in China has exceeded 2,500.

Along with state HEIs, non-state educational institutions also operate in China. Non-state educational institutions established by the public enjoy the same rights as state institutions.

As a result of the accreditation conducted in 1997, only 21 out of 1,200 non-state higher education institutions received the right to issue diplomas of the state model. Non-state higher education institutions are given the right to independently define educational literature and specializations.

Their curricula and programs are focused on the needs of the local economy and aim to fill a gap not covered by public HEIs.

Everyone has to pay for studying in China, the scholarship system applies. Graduates of higher educational institutions are independently employed or enter postgraduate studies.

A Chinese university can send its students abroad for study and internship. In terms of the scope of higher education, China ranks first in the world, and dozens of Chinese universities are well-placed in international rankings of the quality of higher education.

In the latest 2022 ranking of the British magazine "The Times", six Chinese universities are among the 200 best universities in the world. In this list, Peking University is on the 52nd place. The prestige of Chinese business schools has increased. The best of them is Shanghai's CEIBS, which was ranked 22nd among the 100 best schools in 2022 by the Financial Times Executive MBA Rankings.

During the first five years of the reforms, public funding of Chinese higher education institutions more than doubled to \$10.4 billion per year.

Part of the additional costs will be directed to bringing in scientists who have achieved success abroad: they are offered good salaries even by American standards and working conditions similar to those in the West.

Owners of private higher education in China are diverse entities, including: former teachers, retired officials, entrepreneurs; social structures, such as political parties; enterprises, educational groups that play a major role in the organization of private HEIs; branches of the state HEI; HEIs established in cooperation with other countries.

Private higher education institutions have different sources of funding: tuition fees and contributions; funds from sponsors; charitable contributions; bank loans; special state funds; foreign investments; business income and other sources.

Since HEIs do not receive much financial support from the government, the culture of philanthropy in China is not very developed, so most colleges and

universities compete with each other for students who pay a lot of money for education, thus controlling the educational services market.

Korean higher education is both equal and prestigious. On the one hand, the Government consciously and consistently implements the policy of "equal opportunities" for higher education, and on the other hand, Korean higher education institutions form a clear hierarchical pyramid, in which the "evaluation" of diplomas of different universities can be different.

Such a balanced and well-thought-out policy has yielded positive results. By 2005, 97 percent of South Koreans aged 25-34 had a college degree. By comparison, South Korea's national income in the 1960s was lower than that of Mexico and South American countries, and in terms of educational attainment, South Korea was among the most backward countries in the Organization for Economic and Social Development's ranking of 30 countries.

The success achieved is that the country has been able to change the attitude of its population towards education and respond appropriately to the increase in demand. Higher education in Korea is divided into two categories: public or private institutions and vocational institutions (similar to colleges) and universities.

Currently, universities in this country differ greatly in terms of status and ranking, and a degree from one university can open up more opportunities for a graduate than another.

The prestige of a university depends not on its funding status (private or public), but on the scientific potential of the HEI and the quality of its educational programs.

Korean public universities differ from private higher education institutions only in the cost of the study course, for example, the cost of obtaining a bachelor's degree at a public university can be 2 times cheaper than at a private educational institution.

Currently, 419 higher education institutions operating in the Republic of Korea (only 24 of them belong to the state) form a certain "hierarchical pyramid", when the applicant wants to study, he pays attention to the position of the corresponding university in this hierarchy.

Although all universities are controlled by the Ministry of Education and each university has its own curriculum and established teaching skills, the exact university you graduate from in Korea is important.

Therefore, a "good" university diploma plays an important role for its owner in getting a job, later promotion, and even in building his personal life.

Officially, there are 5 types of higher education institutions in Korea, which are: universities, colleges, pedagogical institutes, full-time and part-time universities.

There are also educational institutions with a clear military or religious orientation. In the Republic of Uzbekistan, an effective mechanism for the establishment of foreign university branches and the attraction of enterprises providing foreign educational services to the higher education system has not been introduced.

Malaysia, China, Qatar, UAE and Republic of South Korea should be pointed out as the countries that have implemented similar effective mechanisms and it is bearing fruit.

South Korea's experience of opening branches of foreign state universities in its territory is especially noteworthy. In particular, this country is one of the leading countries in the world in terms of creating a single complex of universities of foreign countries and an innovative approach to this field.

For example, the Global University Complex operates in the Incheon Free Economic Zone of South Korea. Incheon Global University Complex is a project initiated by the Korean government to develop the innovative development of the Korean education system, to educate new generation leaders in the fields of education, economy, industry, culture and art. An investment of 1 billion dollars was made for the implementation of this project.

Currently, there are branches of 10 foreign state universities in this area, in particular, University of Utah, Mason University, Chent University. The goal of the implementation of this project is to join the city of Incheon among the world's leading innovative cities, such as Singapore and Dubai.

Among high-income countries, private financing of higher education averages 29 percent. The increase in private financing of higher education in Korea is not only due to the increase in the number of students enrolled on a fee-contract basis, but also to the increase in the amount of fees for education.

The income from the management of investment assets is directed to the monthly salaries of teachers and researchers, scholarships to students and the financing of the university library and museums.

An investment in an endowment is effectively a perpetual investment. These trust funds are effectively used in many countries of the world and bring 30-40% of their annual income to higher education institutions. In order for higher educational institutions to attract such funds to themselves, first of all, this process requires experienced personnel.

In conclusion, the creative application of the practices of leading foreign universities in the higher educational institutions of our country, taking into account the specific features of our republic, will allow the stabilization of the higher education system in the near future.

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